

Shaped Radome for Wide-Angle mmWave Automotive RADAR

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Abstract—This paper demonstrates a novel radome concept for wide-angle mmWave automotive RADAR antennas. The resulting radomes show superior electrical performance as compared to the industry standard approach. By means of numerical computations, we show that the 5 dB beamwidth is reduced by less than 6° compared with 38° by the proposed and the standard radomes, respectively.

Index Terms—RADAR, Radome, mmWave

I. INTRODUCTION

The radome is an essential component for integrated sensors in many applications. The radome acts as a protective cover which is crucial to maintain the performance of the RF front-end. This is especially important for automotive sensors due to the harsh deployment conditions. Despite the valuable function of the radome, little attention has been put towards the design of this component and is often overlooked. At millimeter wave (mmWave), where state-of-the-art automotive RADAR operates, mechanical constraints play a major role in the design of RF components. Therefore, the industrial standard for automotive radar is based on a flat half-wave cover because of its straightforward implementation. This solution sees little degradation in performance for broadside radiation for which most current RADARs have been designed. However, this solution, as well as more advanced ones, degrade the performance of wide field-of-view (FoV) antennas needed in modern automotive RADARs, as shown in [1].

In this paper, a radome solution is presented which does not deteriorate the performance of the antenna. The focus is on cost-efficient manufacturing techniques such as 3D printing or injection molding.

II. OPTICAL PATH RESCALING

Optical path rescaling (OPR) was first introduced [2] to eliminate dielectric constants smaller than unity, which are typically seen in conformal transformation optics (CTO). In [3] a simplified approach was proposed, where the absolute optical path length could be chosen arbitrarily. This simplification gives more design freedom, with the only consequence of a shift of the absolute radiated phase of the antenna. Since the absolute phase is typically not a concern for antenna design,

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Fig. 1. Schematic view of the mapping from optical path to transmission line

this approach can be used to create a radome. By rescaling the dielectric constant toward the material properties of a given plastic, it is possible to make a radome that does not change the electrical performance of the antenna significantly.

A. transmission line model

OPR allows us to change the dielectric constants based on the optical path of the propagation wave. As long as the change in dielectric constants is parallel to the optical path, no refraction will take place and the optical path remains unchanged. Considering only the radiated power, the direction of the path is equal to the direction of the power flow given by the time average of the Poynting vector \mathbf{P} , given by

$$\mathbf{P} = \frac{1}{2} \text{Re}(\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{H}^*) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} are the radiated Electric and Magnetic fields, $\text{Re}()$ is the operation which takes the real part and $*$ denotes complex conjugate. Based on \mathbf{P} , a mapping can be made from the power flow of the antenna towards a transmission line model, in this mapping the propagation direction from the antenna is mapped to the propagation direction in the transmission line. The cross-section of the transmission line is mapped to the phase-front of the antenna, which are both orthogonal to their respective directions of propagation. A diagram using this mapping is shown in Fig. 1. Using this model, transmission line theory can be applied which allows us to implement structures like quarter-wave transformers, half-wave transformers, etc.

B. Implementation

Based on the model described in Section II-A two radomes are designed. The radomes are designed for a slotted gap waveguide (GW) antenna for wide FoV automotive RADAR.

Fig. 2. Proposed radomes based on two different transmission line transformations, (a) half-wave transformation and (b) quarter-wave transformations.

The two radomes, 'HW_radome' and 'QW_radome', are based on the half-wave (HW) transformer and two quarter-wave (QW) transformers, respectively. The HW_radome is made from a single dielectric material with a dielectric constant of 3.4 similar to a known plastic used for injection molded radome currently on the market. The QW_radome radome also requires a material with a dielectric constant of $\sqrt{3.4} = 1.844$. For our simulations, this material is specified with this material property. However, in practice this may need to be artificially created using a unit cell similar to [4]. To compare these radomes, an additional implementation was made of a radome following the industrial standard, this standard is based on a flat slab of plastic above the antenna of half a wavelength. For consistency, this radome is also placed half a wavelength above the antenna.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 4 shows the return loss of the simulated antenna with the different radomes at the middle of the automotive radar band from 76 – 81 GHz. It can be seen that the introduction of the radomes changes the reflection just slightly. However, the magnitude of the return loss stays below -10 dB over the frequency band from 76 – 81 GHz. As can be seen from Fig. 3, the introduction of the standard radome changes the radiation pattern for wide FoV antennas. Not only is the 5 dB beamwidth reduced from 166° to 128° , but the radome also introduces a ripple on the pattern of 4.4 dB. The two proposed radomes have a 5 dB beamwidth of 162° and 160° and a ripple of 1.95 dB and 1.69 dB for the HW_radome and QW_radome, respectively. The ripple on the reference antenna is 1.38 dB.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has demonstrated a new approach to designing radomes for mmWave automotive RADAR antennas operating from 76 to 81 GHz. Using this method, a protective cover is

Fig. 3. Realized Gain of the antenna.

Fig. 4. Return loss of the antennas, with different radomes

created for the radome, without degrading the radiation performance of the designed antenna. A comparison is made with the current industry standard which indicates an advantage of using the proposed solution.

REFERENCES

- [1] Maruf Md. Sajjad Hossain et al. "Wideband Radomes for Millimeter-Wave Automotive Radars". In: *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation* 70.2 (2022), pp. 1178–1186. DOI: 10.1109/TAP.2021.3118832.
- [2] Hossein Eskandari and Tomas Tyc. "Controlling refractive index of transformation-optics devices via optical path rescaling". In: *Scientific Reports* 9 (Dec. 2019).
- [3] Coen van de Ven, Abolfazl Haddadi, and Andrés Alayón Glazunov. "Automotive RADAR Planar Antenna Optimization Based on Conformal Transformation Optics". In: *EuCAP* (Mar. 2023).
- [4] Juan Lei et al. "Experimental demonstration of conformal phased array antenna via transformation optics". In: *Scientific Reports* 8.1 (Feb. 2018).